

D.6.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy

WP6 – Dissemination and impact

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gEneSys

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Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy

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<i>Abstract</i>	The overarching aim of the gEneSys dissemination and impact activities is to promote (through multiple communication channels), support (e.g., designing and organising participatory events), and enhance opportunities for exploitation of the work and of the results produced by gEneSys to demonstrate that the inclusion of gender equality and gender dimensions in energy transition processes are essential to achieving sustainable, equitable, just, and fair energy transition outcomes.

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1. OVERVIEW OF THE GENESYS DISSEMINATION AND IMPACT STRATEGY

The overarching aim of the gEneSys dissemination and impact activities conducted as [art of WP6 is to promote (through multiple communication channels), support (e.g., designing and organising participatory events), and enhance opportunities for exploitation of the work and of the results produced by gEneSys to demonstrate that the inclusion of gender equality and gender dimensions in energy transition processes are essential to achieving sustainable, equitable, just, and fair energy transition outcomes.

The specific objectives of WP6 are:

- To support the overall objectives and activities of the project following best practice communication and its dissemination strategies and ensure that all project results are made available to all potential change actors, stakeholders, and change recipients, as well as promoting project partners' expertise and experience.
- To broaden the engagement with the multiple target audiences in participatory discourse and processes to achieve consensus on credible pathways and solutions to energy transition with equitable, fair, and just outcomes, focused on intersectional perspective on gender inequality.
- To coordinate project tie-ins to other projects and to the evolving EU energy and equality policy agendas, and to highlight the importance of European collaboration.
- To work with change actors and stakeholders in Africa and in international context to advance gender equality goal of the UN Sustainable Development Agenda 2030 and in research for energy transition.
- To engage and consult the Advisory Board, in consensus building decision making.

Key communication messages explaining what gEneSys is about, and why it is needed are listed in the table below:

<p>What needs does gEneSys responds to</p>	<p>The project responds to policy imperatives at EU and UN levels, and in third partner region in Africa for inclusive approaches to energy transition, and the urgency to incorporate gender perspectives in research and policy design as drivers for achieving sustainable transition to low-carbon world.</p>
<p>What problem will gEneSys help solve</p>	<p>The project identifies that gender has not been a key focus in the policy design and that the connection between gender perspectives and energy policy is under-researched and a connection is needed for these two contemporary challenges to be interlinked in a strategic and operational way.</p>
<p>What new understanding and evidence will gEneSys generate</p>	<p>The project will provide measurable, verifiable, and achievable outcomes by building evidence, scholarly understanding, identifying power holders and facilitating international cooperation between Europe and Africa. The project will advance interdisciplinary, mixed quantitative and qualitative analytical approaches combined with participatory elements and application of gendered innovation analysis.</p>

Who will benefit from gEneSys activities and outputs	Target beneficiaries are women as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, citizens, and consumers; as well as policy makers and experts developing and implementing pathways and solutions for energy transition and green deal, in the EU and in Africa
What outcomes will be achieved	gEneSys will demonstrate gender equality as a lever rather than a barrier to achieving energy transition goals, and will promote actions on gender equality as an outcome of energy transition processes, connecting energy transition with the goals of the EU Green Deal, climate change mitigation and SDGs implementation
How will the objectives and results be shared outside gEneSys	gEneSys will engage multiple target audiences, made up of actors, stakeholders, and participants in energy transition, who share and jointly shape the vision and progress on achieving low-carbon future. The project will help integrate considerations of gender in the science-society-policy dialogue on energy issues and raise awareness of interrelationships of power and intersectional aspects of gender inequality. It will organise two international conference events and create tie-ins with relevant other projects and policy agendas, as well as host a Summer School at Venice International University.

2. EXPLAINING HOW GENESYS IS MEETING THE CHALLENGES HIGHLIGHTED IN THE HORIZON EUROPE CALL UNDER WHICH THE PROJECT WAS FUNDED.

The relevant Horizon Europe Call text specified that proposals are expected to develop a theoretical framework to understand the formation of gendered power hierarchies leading to systematic and structural forms of discriminations, social and economic inequalities, and gender-based violence and should relate this to developing solutions on how to address inequalities and underlying causes related to society's perception and construction of gender norms, masculinities, femininities, and gender diverse identities.

The specific expectations in the Call text include:

- Analysis of the interrelations of power and barriers to gender equality between different social and economic issues including, inter alia: policy and decision-making, labour market participation and the gender pay gap, workplace, and work-life balance arrangements.
- Considerations of how intersectionality of gender with, e.g., ethnicity, social origin, religion, disability, and sexual orientation impacts one's position and rights in society and social hierarchy, as well as one's life and career choices.
- Developing solutions into how to address inequalities and underlying causes related to society's perception and construction of gender norms and representations.
- Promoting international cooperation, as well as the development of social innovation approaches, which can foster new social practices, social ownership, or market uptake.
- Promoting actions to dismantle structural and systematic roots of unequal power distribution between women and men on all levels and promote women's social and

economic empowerment. Particular attention should be paid to differing cultural contexts across the EU and among Associated and third countries.

The project conceptualises energy transition as a gendered socio-technical innovation ecosystem emerging out of the interplay between the technological, policy, social, environmental, governance and economic subsystems. The power relations and inequalities that gEneSys will address will be those within each subsystem, at the intersections between different subsystem, and the system as an ecosystem.

3. GENESYS OBJECTIVES AND ORGANISATION

gEneSys advances understanding of gender and social inequalities in energy transition policies, processes, and outcomes through new research and by closing knowledge gaps in how gender fits into the vision and realisations of just and fair energy transition resulting in the clean, affordable, and secure energy sources and services. This goal relates also to the UN Sustainable Development Agenda 2030, and especially SDG7, which targets “access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy”. In this context gEneSys will cooperate with partners in Africa. In all these cases, the relevant texts are ‘gender blind’ in that they don’t ask for gender-related indicators and don’t specify gender targets. In addition to raising awareness of and supplying new evidence on gender inequality issues in energy transition, gEneSys will improve understanding of “intersectionality” as a research analytical tool as well as a social justice goal.

gEneSys conceptualises energy transition as a dynamic, gendered, mission-oriented socio-technical innovation ecosystem with technological, social, environmental, governance, and economic subsystems, each with its own sustainability visions, implementation concerns, power relations, values and priorities, as well as change actors and stakeholders.

More specifically, gEneSys will respond to the challenges identified in the Horizon Europe Call by:

- cooperating with partners in Africa through its own African partner, the African Institute for Mathematical Science, and external collaborating organisations and/or projects working towards the EU’s and UN’s mission to supply/ensure access to affordable and secure energy, and to show how to integrate gender perspectives into implementations of SDG7 targets and achieve gender equality benefits.
- improving understanding of “inclusion” by raising awareness of the intersectional aspects of gender inequality in relation to energy transition through the analysis of existing data and by collecting, analysing, and theorising original data collected through extensive surveys.
- reviewing EU and national energy-related frameworks to identify the extent to which gender mainstreaming is being implemented.
- examining available statistics on the participation and roles that women hold in energy-related sectors as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and employees. It will also collect new data to understand the behaviours and attitudes to energy transition of women and men as citizens and consumers.

- assembling gender evidence base for transformative climate and environmental policies with an intersectional approach to reduce climate and environmental impacts while challenging patriarchal and other discriminatory structures.
- applying gender lens to the 400 priority SSH research questions recommended by the EU Energy SHIFTS project to support appropriately designed studies with intersectional aspects of gender dimension fully considered.
- improving understanding how countries can use the shift towards sustainable energy to tackle systemic gender discrimination within societies.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE DISSEMINATION AND IMPACT WORK PACKAGE (WP6)

The overarching aim of WP6 is to promote (through multiple communication channels), support (e.g., designing and organising participatory events), and enhance opportunities for exploitation of the work and results of gEneSys to demonstrate how gender equality and gender dimensions in research can improve design and implementation of energy transition pathways and processes to achieve sustainability and outcomes that are equitable, just, and fair.

The specific objectives of the dissemination activities are:

- To share information about project objectives, activities and results and make them available to all potential change actors, stakeholders, and change recipients, as well creating opportunities to enhance project partners' expertise, experience, and status in the research community.
- To ensure engagement with multiple target audiences through participatory dialogue and activities aimed at achieving consensus on credible pathways and solutions to energy transition with equitable, fair, and just outcomes, and advancing intersectional perspective on energy related gender and social inequalities.
- To coordinate project tie-ins to other projects and to the evolving EU energy and equality policy agendas, and to highlight the importance of European collaboration in achieving gender equality.
- To work with change actors and stakeholders in Africa and in international context to advance gender equality goal of the UN Sustainable Development Agenda 2030 and in research for energy transition.
- To engage and consult the Advisory Board, who have been selected for their specific areas of expertise that matched the aims of the Work Plan, in consensus building decision making.

5. MANAGEMENT AND ORGANISATION OF THE DISSEMINATION AND IMPACT STRATEGY

Portia is tasked with the overall leadership and management of the work towards the objectives of WP6, with all other partners acting as co-leads and or contributors. In total, WP6 include five distinct Tasks. One task is dedicated to supporting the project partners; three tasks are dedicated to engaging with multiple target audiences in the energy

transition ecosystem; and one task is dedicated to hosting a Summer School, which is led by VIU and CNR.

5.1 Sharing experiences, results, and goals with target communities

gEneSys will establish direct connections and collaborations with projects, initiatives and programmes in the energy transition socio-technical innovation ecosystem that have either 1) already developed support measures for gender equality, or 2) plan/wish to do so, or 3) have not considered gender equality as relevant to their mission but should do so (e.g., if receiving funding as part of the EU Cohesion strategy or Horizon Europe).

In these exchanges, gEneSys will aim to advance and harmonise understanding and activities related to the questions below:

- How to overcome gender inequalities in existing energy systems, and how to prevent these inequalities occurring in the renewable and low carbon energy systems?
- How to mainstream gender into new policy frameworks that underpin energy transition and European Green Deal?
- How to integrate gender perspective into energy transition processes and outcomes, including the targets of the UN Sustainable Development Goals Agenda 2030?
- How to advance women in energy ecosystem as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, leaders, employees, and consumers?
- How to measure and monitor gender equality in relation to achieving justice and fairness in energy transition outcomes?
- How to promote shared values of equity, sustainability, participation, and diversity across the social, economic, environmental, and technical spheres of energy transition?
- How to respond to intersectional dimensions of gender equality in societal debates on access to energy, energy security, energy poverty and affordability, environmental impacts, etc.?
- How social innovation can facilitate transformations of existing power hierarchies in energy transition planning and management?
- How can research help facilitate greater societal acceptance of the changes on people's lives created by energy transition measures, and how to fully include women at all levels of energy-related knowledge production, application, and communication?
- How can approaches and understanding of energy transition processes be made more sensitive to gender issues through systematic gender mainstreaming, gender budgeting, use of Gendered Innovations analysis, Multistakeholder Partnerships, Communities of Practice, Gender Equality Plans, Responsible Research & Innovation?

6. EXPECTED IMPACTS OF GENESYS

6.1 Promoting understanding of energy transition as a socio-technical innovation ecosystem

gEneSys conceptualises energy transition as a dynamic, gendered, mission-oriented socio-technical innovation ecosystem with several 'subsystems': technological, policy, social, environmental, governance, and economic, each with its own sustainability visions, values, and priorities, as well as change actors and stakeholder, who may also influence what happens in other subsystems.

Women are underrepresented at all levels and in all areas of energy-related decision making and as such they are excluded from energy transition decision-making processes, and this may reinforce existing inequalities. For instance, research shows that low-carbon transitions and climate mitigation efforts can involve power struggles and processes of exacerbating vulnerability, and, critically, the "greening" of energy systems may not make them any fairer, inclusive, or just without recognition of and specific interventions to address gender concerns.

gEneSys envisages energy transition as shaped by several 'subsystems': technological, policy, social, environmental, governance, and economic, each with its own power structures, sustainability visions, values, and priorities, as well as change actors and stakeholder. What happens in any individual subsystem may also influence what may happen in other subsystems, offering opportunities to reduce competitive relationships and enhance opportunities for creating synergies oriented towards the expectations in the EU Gender Equality Strategy that all programmes and agencies adopt gender mainstreaming objectives.

6.1.1 Policy subsystem

Many disparities and inequalities between the sexes have become historically embedded in the baseline of public policies and in the allocation of public resources. The EU is officially committed to mainstreaming gender equality into policymaking together with targeted actions to tackle gender-blindness and gender-bias in policy design and practice. Gender mainstreaming and environmental policy integration are both EU treaty-based obligations. This means that gender equality and environmental objectives must be mainstreamed or integrated into all areas of EU policymaking, including sectors where they are not immediately obvious. Of particular interest are the concerns that the most recent policy frameworks, e.g., the EU Just Transition Mechanism, LIFE Clean Energy Transition, and REPower still appear to be gender blind.

6.1.2 Economic subsystem

Compared to other parts of the economy, energy is one of the most gender unequal sectors. Women are underrepresented in both traditional and emerging energy sectors, at all levels. Much of the discourse on the effects of energy transition has focused on the impact on men's jobs and on their skills needs for future jobs. Jobs in renewable energy tend to be scattered across different areas of employment, such as manufacturing, construction, installation, fuel processing, operations and maintenance, and specific information related to gender equality in the renewables sector is seldom captured in national statistics. In this context, gender budgeting is an important tool to ensure that financing of energy transition programmes and processes shifts towards outcomes that support and improve gender equality across all energy sectors.

6.1.3 Environmental subsystem

Some of the most vulnerable groups in energy transition are those that own, operate, or use the climate mitigation options, or those working on the manufacturing of those options at mines, processing facilities, or factories, or in the disposal of waste. For instance, many communities hosting wind farms, residing on land being proposed for biofuel crop cultivation, living in shared forests or nature reserves, or sitting adjacent to solar parks bear the brunt of negative and often concentrated social and environmental impacts. Technologically driven energy transition interventions can also impact negatively on natural ecosystem that humans depend on for their livelihood and wellbeing. Energy transition pathways and solutions require environmental, social, economic, and sustainability assessment across their whole lifecycle.

6.1.4 Socio-cultural subsystem

Frequently, social inequalities in low-carbon transitions are presented as four distinct power processes: enclosure (capture of land or resources), exclusion (unfair planning), encroachment (destruction of the environment), or entrenchment (worsening of inequality or vulnerability). But culture and social norms and habits can complicate and impede attempts to promote more efficient, more sustainable, and more affordable forms of energy use in homes and in buildings. Everyday routines, habits, social behaviours, aesthetic preferences and locked-in logics of consumption and mobility are important features of and may constitute significant barriers to abandoning dependence on fossil fuel-based

energy system. Users don't adopt new technologies passively, but integrate them into their own practices, organisations, and routines.

6.1.5 Governance subsystem

Low-carbon transition pathways can entrench or cement existing power relations, including those among influential groups, advocates, political parties, or governments, where men are better integrated than women. Exclusion of women from decision-making means that alternative views and different ways of argumentation and engaging in alternative efforts to achieve the goals of the European Green Deal may be overlooked. Achieving equitable and fair energy transition means making governance more inclusive, tackling exclusion, and promoting shared prosperity and equity. It is fundamentally about altering underlying power structures and dynamics and redefining state-society relations. The extent to which governance is inclusive has to do with the extent to and ways in which people and groups that have been traditionally left out or marginalised (including women; young people; racial, ethnic, and religious groups; disabled people, transient and migrant populations, etc.) are able not only to participate but also to exert greater influence in political processes for energy transition.

6.1.6 Technological subsystem

Women are underrepresented and undervalued in STEM sectors, but the R&I energy research landscape is highly diverse in the range of disciplines involved and this can facilitate new career pathways and opportunities to attract more women to energy related research, innovation, and entrepreneurship. The available pool of female talent is seriously underutilised and undervalued through numerous barriers to women's participation in energy transition at all levels, which means women do not get the same opportunity as men to shape future energy systems or the 'greening' of the economy. Currently, the share of women in the renewable energy sector is marginally higher compared to the conventional energy sector, which suggests that the emerging energy areas appear to be more attractive and more welcoming to women, however, this positive image does not apply to decision-making and leadership roles. Combined with the growing interest in climate issues, particularly among young women, energy transition requires fresh, gender sensitive policy responses to accelerate actions.

7. LEARNING FROM THE EFFORTS OF PAST PROJECTS

gEneSys recognises the work of many past EU projects dedicated to advancing gender equality in research and innovation. It also draws on projects dedicated to advancing energy transition by paying attention to the social aspects of transition processes. Majority of the projects conducted so far have not included considerations of gender issues or have done so in a very limited way. gEneSys will identify and map project partnerships and extract useful lessons from the results of past projects such as: GEECCO, CALIPER, MINDtheGEPs, EFFORTI, ACT, INSPIRE, SocialRES, SONNET, PROSEU, Energy-SHIFTS, MATES RES-SKILL, W4RES, REGATRACE, ENTRANCES, GROWINPRO, EXCESS, SmartENCity, and SCALIBUR.

During the first six months of the project, the dissemination strategy focused on mapping the current institutional landscape where energy transition efforts are decided and acted upon. A total of over 100 entities operating in the EU have been identified. Several of these entities

are umbrella organisations, therefore gEneSys will be able to reach out to many more organisations.

8. BUILDING RELATIONS WITH CURRENT PROJECTS AND PROGRAMMES

During the first six months of the project, dissemination efforts established collaborative links aimed at sharing of the efforts on issues of mutual concern with currently active EU initiatives, projects, networks, including:

- the DG CINEA-funded project to develop gender indicators for energy transition R&I
- LEAP-RE programme that has funded 31 projects on renewable energy under the EU-AU cooperation
- FemPower, Erasmus project
- RESET, Horizon 2020 project
- INSPIRE, Horizon Europe project
- Light on Women initiative of the European University Institute
- 23rd Gender Summit – Africa, in energy transition and green deal in Africa
- EUREC – association of European renewable research centres
- Women Engage for a Common Future (WECF)

Since gEneSys conceptualises energy transition as a mission-led innovation ecosystem, the plans for sustainable actions will be formulated once the network of relevant actor and stakeholder organisations is created making interactions and dialogue among different entities from each subsystem more securely established using the planned mechanisms, namely events, conferences, webinars, etc. Early targets have been listed in Section 2.4 above.

8.1 Identifying indicators of successful impact of energy transition efforts on gender equality

gEneSys has established close links with the DG CINEA-funded contract project which aims to develop gender indicators for energy transition R&I. These results will become available towards the end of 2023. In addition, the project will analyse how gender-equality is expressed in the 35 available gender-related indicator sets to see if there are data already collected that are relevant to gender equality in energy transition.

The desired categories of gender equality indicators should provide insights into:

- Added value of gender equality for energy transition research and innovation
- Added value for policy
- Added value for society
- Sustainability and capacity building for energy transition implementation efforts
- Communication and dissemination effects, and
- Project management and delivery

9. TRACKING GENESYS IMPACT ON ENERGY TRANSITION EFFORTS IN THE EU AND AFRICA

The tracking of gEneSys impact on the energy transition policy, research, and implementation landscape will aim to:

- Continue to identify knowledge needs
- Continue to develop activities to deliver those needs
- Map the timing of opportunities to feed into the policy processes and R&I projects landscape
- Continue to revise and adapt efforts to identify and engage with diverse audiences.

WHAT?	HOW?	WHEN?	FOR WHO?
What new knowledge, evidence and examples of best practice are needed that gEneSys can provide?	Through which project tasks and activities can gEneSys produce the required knowledge?	What is the opportunity timeline in target projects, programmes, and initiatives that gEneSys has to keep in mind to have the intended impact?	Who are the target audiences that need new knowledge (perhaps tailored to their special needs)?

10. TARGET USERS AND BENEFICIARIES OF THE RESULTS PRODUCED BY GENESYS AND THE KNOWLEDGE THEY MAY NEED

End users/beneficiaries	Knowledge needs
Policy makers	
e.g., European Parliament	e.g., Reliable research evidence addressing key policy issues
EU agencies and programmes	
e.g., DG Energy DG RTD/Horizon Europe programme DG REGIO/Cohesion programme DG CINEA/Gender Indicators project	e.g., Research evidence and expert analyses for more effective mainstreaming of gender into programmes and policy implementation tools
R&I funding institutions	
e.g., Science Europe NordForsk Vinnova DFG JRC EIC HEA Ireland NIKK Swedish Energy Agency	e.g., - evidence how to harmonise funding on gender equality in energy-related programmes

International organisations/initiatives	
e.g., UN Women IRENA IEA EERA EAWE	e.g., integrating gender perspectives into implementations of SDG7
R&I performing organisations	
e.g., European Universities Association CESAER LERU	e.g., - gender perspective on what universities can do for energy transition - how to attract women to energy-related courses
Civil Society, NGOs, Networks	
e.g., Women in Renewable Energy Women in CleanTech & Sustainability	e.g., career opportunities in energy transition
Horizon Europe projects	
e.g., GEP and gender dimension implementing projects FemEmpower	e.g., examples of gender analyses in the context of energy transition/climate change/green deal
National-level projects and programmes	
e.g., Swedish Energy Agency programme on societal alternatives for energy transition solutions	e.g., gender sensitive analyses of societal research questions
Participants in gEneSys surveys and consultations	
e.g., Organisations/communities in Africa participating in citizen surveys	e.g., conceptualisations, definitions, and survey best practice on gender sensitive data collection
Journalists and Social Media	
e.g., Horizon, the EU R&I Magazine Energy4Europe Africa-EU Energy Partnership	e.g., results and lessons from the project
Think Tanks	
e.g., CERRE EEI	e.g., energy related scholarly gender expertise

11. ADDING STAKEHOLDER VALUE IN THE EXPLOITATION EFFORTS OF GENESYS RESULTS

gEneSys dissemination and exploitation measures are designed to add value and promote additional outcomes based on the project's results, deliverables, and outcomes from interconnections with other projects and initiatives in the energy transition ecosystem, as well as opportunities created under Erasmus+ funded projects and national NCP networks, as well as Horizon Europe NCP networks.

Key exploitable results	Target audience	Adding Value
Academic and policy publications, both peer-reviewed and as working papers, new research evidence, questions, analyses of gender dimension, results as ideas for special issue journals, fresh topics of conferences, topics for PhD, recommendations for curriculum change	Research communities, research managers, research funders, research communicators, and research editors in Europe and Africa + European Commission, African Union, and UN Agencies	Strengthening the evidence base for the EU policy strategy on gender equality in R&I, especially in Horizon Europe & the European Green Deal
The model of energy transition as a mission-oriented, gendered, innovative socio-technical ecosystem together with credible pathways to transform interrelations of power and inequality to achieve equitable, just, and fair outcomes for women and men	Policy makers, decision-makers, industry, education, Civil society/citizen organisations	Opportunities shared, implementable agendas, multistakeholder partnerships of change actors and stakeholders, greater societal engagement
Tested analytical approaches for international cooperation on gender sensitive implementation of SDGs and especially SDG7 (energy) with gender equality outcomes	Gender equality, SDG, and sustainability experts and practitioners	Integration of gender perspectives into all the SDG targets
Supplementary gender analysis with gender dimensions added to the 400 SSH priority research questions to	SSH and gender researchers, as well as experts and policy makers	Strengthening the evidence base and interconnections between gender and social aspect of Responsible Research and Innovation
Review of policy frameworks relevant to energy transition with opportunities/needs for gender mainstreaming	EU and national policy makers and policy impact evaluation experts	Advancing gender mainstreaming for gender equality in climate change mitigation efforts, Green New Deal, SDGs implementation, and decarbonisation goals
Demonstrations of applying tools for sex/gender analysis in research and innovation content	Research and innovation communities, research and innovation funders	Support for proposals to Horizon Europe and evaluation of impact
International Summer School at Venice University	Students	Dissemination of the principles of equity, justice and fairness in

		energy transition to student population
Curriculum and outreach programme to schools	Education communities, citizens	Holistic approach to energy transitions with better transfer of knowledge
Website/social presence	Everybody	Improving and widening the communication of evidence

12. DIALOGUE AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING WITH STAKEHOLDERS IN ENERGY

GEneSys will engage with the change actors and stakeholders in the six subsystems: political, social, economic, environmental, and technical to fully understand and influence the conceptualisations of interrelationships of power and inequality in the context of energy transitions to be more sensitive and responsive to gender inequality issues and to seeing gender equality as a lever in achieving transition.

12.1 Dialogue to promote the Gendered Innovations analytical framework

To help relevant projects and initiatives in Europe and Africa to apply gender analysis tools and intersectional perspectives to understand the barriers and obstacles to achieving equitable, inclusive, and sustainable outcomes, gEneSys will identify knowledge gaps in how gender dimension is understood in the energy transition ecosystem; how it is discussed in the context of the ambitions to ensure that results are just, fair and inclusive; and how to analyse gender dimensions of energy transition in a systematic way using the Gendered Innovations framework of 11 areas of analysis:

1. Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes which means accepting that gender differences are or may be relevant. In the context of energy transition this is particularly important when assembling the evidence base to support analysis of individual subsystems and their interactions with one another.
2. Rethinking Concepts and Theories which means unpacking definitions (e.g., “energy transition”) and clarifying understanding of the wording used when energy transition is debated, e.g., “just transition”, “energy poverty” etc. This helps understand the influence of formal and informal social institutions, social norms, and gender stereotypes of human behaviour.
3. Formulating Research Questions which is about scoping the analytical approach to identify gender-related power hierarchies in energy systems (traditional and emerging). The relevant gender question can be for instance how to ensure societal acceptance of radical innovations and understand impacts of environmental degradation of energy infrastructures on women's livelihoods and health.
4. Analysing Sex means paying attention to essential, unchangeable biological differences and how they influence response to energy poverty, hunger, disease, or changes in environmental conditions, for instance due to polluting household cooking equipment.
5. Analysing Gender means understanding socio-cultural norms and stereotypes used in society to label an individual as male or female and recognising how socio-cultural

differences and inequalities between women and men are maintained by social institutions.

6. Analysing how Sex and Gender Interact means considering both biological and socio-cultural perspectives on the role and behaviours of women and men. For instance, tracking impact of greenhouse gas emissions may involve understanding the gendered nature of energy consumption as it relates to work, or within the household, and how it relates to health and wellbeing.
7. Intersectional Approaches means paying attention to other human characteristics such as age, social status, education, ethnicity, race, geography, that play a role in defining vulnerability through lack of access to energy supply.
8. Engineering Innovation Processes means creating socio-technical systems to ensure that energy transition pathways and low-carbon technologies do not propagate gender inequalities embedded in existing technologies. As an example, solar panels are particularly difficult to dismantle, which makes attempts to recycle the components very difficult, contributing to accumulation of electronic waste, but also restricting opportunities for creating employment for women in electronic waste processing sector.
9. Co-creation and Participatory Research means involving multiple actors and stakeholders in analysis of problems and generation of proposals for solutions. In the context of energy transitions this may mean including the voices of rural, poor, indigenous, or other marginalized communities.
10. Rethinking Standards and Reference Models means removing gender bias in energy transition through, for example, enhancing transparency and traceability in procurement of resources, products, and services to ensure availability and price of energy.
11. Rethinking Language and Visual Representations means demonstrating the gendered nature of energy transition in a way that can be easily comprehended by non-gender experts and lay persons. This could be by using images, graphics, stories when communicating rationales for gendered energy transitions etc.

12.2 Dialogue focused on the policy subsystem

The key elements in the policy subsystem for gEneSys are the 2020-2025 Gender Equality Strategy (GES) and the third Gender Action Plan (GAPIII), the 2021-2027 Multi-annual Financial Framework (MFF), Horizon Europe, and the 2021-2027 Cohesion Plan and Fund. The key objectives of GES are: ending gender-based violence; challenging gender stereotypes; closing gender gaps in the labour market; achieving equal participation across different sectors of the economy; addressing the gender pay and pension gaps; closing the gender care gap; and achieving gender balance in decision-making and in politics. The 2021–2027 MFF includes a gender dimension throughout, and more specifically in various EU funding and budgetary guarantee instruments (particularly ESF+, the ERDF, Creative Europe, the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund, the Cohesion Fund and the InvestEU programme). Funding will support women's labour market participation and work-life balance, invest in care facilities, support female entrepreneurship, combat gender segregation in certain professions and address the unbalanced representation of girls and boys in parts of education and training. Monitoring of progress on gender equality in MFF uses three criteria:

- Score 01 Gender targeting for actions making a targeted positive contribution to gender equality – Interventions whose principal objective is to contribute to gender equality; improving gender equality is the main objective of the intervention, without it the action would probably not exist.

- Score 02 Gender mainstreaming for actions making a positive contribution to gender equality through mainstreaming – Interventions having gender equality as an important and deliberate objective but not as the main reason for the intervention; gender equality is directly or indirectly improved as a side effect of the core actions.
- Score 03 Gender neutral for actions that are gender neutral – interventions that do not target or contribute to gender equality.

gEneSys policy-related dissemination efforts will target several DGs involved in promoting gender equality actions interconnected to achieving just and fair energy transition, including DG RTD, DG ENERGY, DG CLIMA, DG EMPL, DG JRC DG REGIO

12.3 Dialogue focused on the technology subsystem

The focus of dissemination activities in the technological subsystem will be the European Strategic Energy Technology Plan, its nine European Technology Innovations Platforms, and the members of the European Energy Research Alliance (250 organisations in 30 countries) who are at the forefront of technological innovation. In addition, gEneSys will aim to enrich understanding how gender fits into the recommendations made in the 2017 EUA report on Energy Transition and the Future of Energy Research, Innovation and Education: An Action Agenda for European Universities.

The EUA report stresses that achieving a low carbon economy involves tackling uncertainty and ambiguity about future energy supply, the energy mix, energy use and efficiency and working out how to address behavioural change and adaptation, and that universities are key stakeholders in energy transition. These dissemination actions are needed because of the persistent underrepresentation of women in SET fields reported by She Figures.

gEneSys will engage with stakeholders advancing technological solutions for energy transition, as well as with the EU (virtual) multidisciplinary Energy Transition Expertise Centre (EnTEC), created to monitor and analyse trends in technologies and innovations that are relevant for the energy transition, in the energy sector but also in other relevant sectors, including the organisation that have participated in the EUA consultation.

12.4 Dialogue focused on society

In relation to the societal subsystem, the gEneSys dissemination activities will raise awareness of the missed gender dimensions in the evidence and outcomes of several recent EU energy related projects such as the EU Energy-Shifts project, which identified 400 social science and humanities priority research questions in four energy areas (100 questions each): renewables, smart consumption, energy efficiency and transport and mobility.

One of the gEneSys consortium partners, Jagiellonian University, has been involved in the Energy-Shifts project and will take this task on. Other projects where gender dimension needs analysis include: ECHOES and its theoretical concepts of 'energy collectives' and 'energy memories'; ENABLE.EU which conducted household surveys to understand the factors that drive energy choices in daily life; ENERGISE, which developed methods to transform energy use in households; SMARTEES which developed the concept of social energy innovation; CHEETAH which assessed how policy interventions break down barriers to energy efficient choices; PENNY, which studied psychological, social, economic and financial factors in the residential sectors, and ASSET that addressed the challenge of a

rapidly evolving energy sector that requires creating new job opportunities, re-skilling the workforce, and the development of new interdisciplinary skills and expertise.

In the first stage of the gEneSys project, dissemination activities involving the societal subsystem will be the gender content of the Energy-Shifts recommendations, and ongoing projects, such as FemPower, the Lights on Women initiative, and the many women's networks across different areas of the renewable energy sectors.

12.5 Dialogue focused on environment

The gEneSys dissemination activities in the context of environmental subsystem will focus on the EU strategy for achieving net-zero GHG emissions by 2050 while sustaining economic growth as set out in the European Green Deal (COM(2019)640 final) and has been followed by legislative texts, including the 2021 Climate Law. There was no Impact Assessment conducted for the 2021 Climate Law. European Union (EU) energy policies aim to deliver on the EU's Paris Agreement commitments through a Clean Energy Transition which encourages greater efficiency, and the use of low carbon energy sources to replace fossil fuels.

The EU clean and fair energy transition aims to create a more secure, competitive, and sustainable energy system that supports economic growth and improves the quality of life of its citizens. EU Clean energy for all Europeans legislative acts aim to place the citizen at the centre of the energy transition.

12.6 Dialogue focused on governance

The new energy policy is Europe's response to the impacts of COVID pandemic and the war in Ukraine is the REPowerEU policy priority for more affordable, secure, and sustainable energy. The European Green Capital is relevant to understand transitions in labour markets. Strongly relevant to the advancement of gender equality in energy sectors is the EU Directive on Work-life Balance, Recast Directive (2006/54/EC on gender equality and non-discrimination, developments in ERA and EHEA, the European Social Charter of the Council of Europe, Ljubljana Declaration, and the European Parliament's call for Cooperation between EU and Africa on SDGs.

gEneSys dissemination at the governance subsystem level will target, in particular, the European Commission's DG Budget to help identify programmes where realisation of gender equality benefits in the funded programmes can be accelerated, and at the European Parliament's level the FEMM and ITRE Committees that can influence political attitudes to gender equality in energy transition, as well as the EP Research Services, in relation to the policy briefings the Service produces.

12.7 Dialogue focused on Africa and SDGs

Ensuring a joint EU-AU Green transition means working together towards a low-carbon, resource efficient and climate-resilient future in line with the Paris Agreement. The EU addresses these priorities through its European Green Deal, complemented by the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, the EU Farm to Fork Strategy and others. The AU guiding continental flagship is Africa' Agenda 2063, with the CAADP and Malabo Declaration, the AU SPS Policy Framework, the AU Wildlife Strategy, the AU

Sustainable Forest Management Framework, the AU Blue Economy Strategy and others contributing to it.

Promote gender equality perspectives in the targets of Agenda 2030: targeting UN agencies and initiatives, especially, UN Women, High-level Dialogue on Energy, Agenda 2030 High level Political Reviews, National Voluntary Reports, and Global Sustainable Development Report, establishing opportunities to impact on the directions and alignment of policy discussions on future implementation strategies.

gEneSys dissemination activities in this part of the project have used the 2023 Gender Summit – Africa on Africa's energy transition pathways and green deal to engage with actors outside the Consortium. Following from this event, gEneSys has connected with the EU-AU collaborative program LEAP-RE, which has funded 31 projects on developing renewable energy solutions to take joint actions on advancing gender dimension and gender equality benefits into these projects.

13. ON-LINE ACCESS TO KEY RESOURCES

gEneSys aim is to make its website as the target for up-to-date, impactful information, advice, and co-operation activities on advancing understanding of gender issues in energy transition. For this, gEneSys will post its own resources: the outputs and deliverables from the different work packages and links to the key resources that underpin the projects work. It will also feature important resources produced by the organisations with whom the project will co-operate, such as topical research review-based blogs, learning materials, guidelines etc.

14. CONFERENCES AND EVENTS

gEneSys will prioritise opportunities for speaker-level participation in conferences and events but also will endeavour to take part in events where virtual participation is enabled. gEneSys will organise two international conference events (~300 registered participants each) and six participatory workshops/webinars (~60 participants each) as part of work packages 1-5 to explore energy transition as a gendered, innovative socio-economic ecosystem and establish how socialization of 'green' energy technology and knowledge can be accelerated by using gender equality policy as a lever in public involvement.

Since the project has started, the project was represented in the following events:

- Public event introducing gEneSys organised as part of the kick-off meeting (March 2023)
- As a dedicated speaker panel made up of Consortium Partners, in a parallel on-line session in the 23rd Gender Summit – Africa, which had as the theme Africa's energy transition pathways and green deal through the gender lens (May 2023)
- Interactive Exhibition Booth at GS23 on-line conference platform
- As speakers and moderators in the in-person GS23 programme that took place in Ghana

- The European Sustainable Energy Conference, as participant (May 2023)
- The Light on Women awards event, as participant (June 2023)

Forthcoming in 2023 are:

- The International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators, as member of the in-person special session speaker panel (September 2023)
- Consultation workshop on gender indicators in energy transition R&I, as invited participant (October 2023)
- 24th Gender Summit – Europe, as invited speakers (November 2023)

Later in the project, gEneSys will organise a one-week summer school hosted by the Venice International University (VIU) in Venice that will involve 20 students from different countries. Students will be selected through an open call that will be disseminated through the consortium partners' networks, as well as, through the Venice International University network that includes universities and research institutions from North America, Europe, Africa, Middle East, and Asia.

15. COMMUNICATION

gEneSys achieves impact by pro-actively promoting gender equality as a lever (rather than a barrier) in achieving equitable, just, and fair processes and outcomes in energy transition, the European Green Deal, climate change mitigation efforts, and SDGs implementation. An example target are members of the European Energy Research

Alliance with more than 175 research organisations from 27 countries, involved in 17 joint programmes. Communication efforts will aim to promote multistakeholder, multidisciplinary understanding of the consequences of gender inequality and their intersectional aspects

in energy transition and in the sustainability goals, and of the need for inclusive and shared responsibility of power and decision making to achieve equitable, fair and just processes and outcomes.

16. WEBSITE

The website aims to provide information about the project itself and its goals but also to act as a source of gender-related information for organisations and projects active in energy transition processes:

- To help change actors and stakeholders in the six subsystems: political, social, economic, environmental, and technical to improve their understanding of the interrelationships of power and inequality in the context of energy transitions and be more sensitive and responsive to gender inequality issues and to seeing gender equality as a lever in achieving transition.
- To promote the project's vision of energy transition as a mission-oriented, gendered, socio-technical innovation ecosystem and open multiple opportunities for fresh discourses on how different institutions/sectors and professions can shape the conceptual landscape of energy transition to create robust and socially responsible technological innovations that are equitable, fair, and just.
- To point out example of gender blind or biased thinking and the consequences of gender inequality and their intersectional aspects in energy transition and in the sustainability goals,
- To shape evidence and arguments to ensure well focused and implementable recommendations for action at the level of policy, knowledge, technology, societal involvement, and socio-economic development that respond to the agendas of the different change actors and stakeholders in energy transition.
- To improve understanding of power-gender relations, processes, and outcomes in energy transition and better agendas for gender equality in the European Green Deal, climate change mitigation efforts and Sustainable Development Goals.

16.1 Communication channels and materials

gEneSys has established a visual identity and a presence on LinkedIn and Twitter. Collaborative links have been established with the European Universities Institute and the Horizon 2020 programme LEAP-RE, as well as the CINEA-funded project developing gender indicators for energy transition R&I.

Interactive exhibition booth at the 23rd Gender Summit - Africa

specific channels and measures that will be targeted are summarised below.

Channels	Materials and outputs
Academic and policy publications	<p>Expected</p> <p>2 x research papers submitted/year, 3 x Working Papers, and 6 x policy briefs</p> <p>Achieved/forthcoming</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A report from the 23rd Gender Summit – Africa • Joint analysis with European Universities Institute on how the women in their Light on Women Database perceive power relations in the energy areas they work in
Presentations	<p>Expected:</p> <p>6 x conference presentations in external events</p> <p>Achieved/forthcoming</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May 2023: presentation at the 23rd Gender Summit-Africa • September 2023: presentation at the International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators • November 2023: presentation at the 24th Gender Summit-Europe
Synergistic interlinkages with change actors, stakeholders, and projects	<p>Expected:</p> <p>6 x joint activities (webinars, high level dialogues, joint workshops/co-creation events)</p> <p>Achieved/forthcoming</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinar with the European Universities Institute on careers in energy transition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars with LEAP-RE on gender equality issues in renewable energy • Webinar with GISTeR on gender innovation indicators

Policy workshops	<p>Expected: 3 x workshops 30-40 attendees (in person and on-line)</p> <p>Achieved/forthcoming</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As part of INSPIRE project policy workshop – to help contextualise policy recommendations on gender equality to include energy and green deal (October 2023) • As part of Empirica project on gender indicators in energy Transition R&I – to help validate perspectives on gender equality in energy transition scenarios (October 2023)
Social media	<p>Expected: 1000 followers</p>
Website	<p>Expected: 10,000 hits</p>
Conference	<p>Expected: 300 attendees</p>
Project information	Leaflets, posters, summaries

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